

Process Design for GOVAQUA Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations

GOVAQUA Deliverable 6.1

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The background and purpose of the document

The Horizon Europe-funded GOVAQUA project (2023-2027) identifies, assesses, further develops and validates water governance instruments and approaches needed for a transition to sustainable and equitable water use in Europe.

At the heart of GOVAQUA are six newly established Living Labs (Figure 1) which will act as real-life testing grounds for legal and regulatory, participatory and collaborative, economic and financial, and digital innovations in different EU Member State Settings. Besides engaging in co-creation processes with the Living Lab stakeholders in quest of new solutions, the GOVAQUA project tests the Living Lab approach itself as an innovative participatory way to develop water governance for a transition to sustainable and equitable water use, evaluating its effectiveness and fairness.

Figure 1. GOVAQUA Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations.

The purpose of this guidance document is to establish a joint process design for the GOVAQUA project Living Labs. It will 1) guide the GOVAQUA Living Lab leaders on how to set up, develop and assess their respective Living Labs, and collect findings for broader recommendations and lesson learning, and 2) guide the other partners in linking their project work to the Living Lab processes.¹

All the GOVAQUA Living Labs build on pre-existing multi-stakeholder collaboration initiatives with direct linkages to public water management and governance institutions. The project introduces the three stages of *Exploration*, *Experimentation* and *Evaluation* of the innovation process (Malmberg et al. 2017) with a preceding *Initiation and preparation* phase (Rădulescu et al. 2022) to their co-creation settings, and the

¹ This document has been prepared during the first months of the GOVAQUA project. Hence, the process design might be subject to changes depending on the project findings and proceedings. Final GOVAQUA project recommendations on the Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations are due at the end of the project, benefiting from lessons learned from applying the process design in the six GOVAQUA Living Labs in question.

respective Living Lab project teams act as facilitators and knowledge providers during the project duration.

As Living Labs, the GOVAQUA interventions are unique with their specific focus on water governance. While Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLs) are well established in Europe and currently further developed under the Water4All partnership with the leadership of Water Europe, they tend to focus on technological solutions, and the related development work has, to date, emphasised maturity assessments of existing Living Labs rather than methodologies for building new ones (Water Europe 2022, Water4All Partnership 2023). GOVAQUA will contribute to the WOLLs methodology development bringing in lessons learned in establishing new Labs and expanding the scope of innovations in focus to “good practices” spanning from technological solutions to broader governance arrangements, and closer linking Living Labs to multi-level sustainability transitions needed.

The document is structured as follows: the next section “Living Labs – definitions and methodologies” describes the Living Lab approach origins, definitions and key methodologies laying the foundation for the methodological framework applied in the GOVAQUA Living Labs. Section “GOVAQUA Living Lab process design” details the key aspects to consider, tools and methods, and linkages to the overall project processes for the Initiation and preparation, Exploration, Experimentation and Evaluation phases of the Living Labs during the project duration. Section “Living Labs coordination and synthesis of lessons learned” details how the findings from the GOVAQUA Living Labs will be collected, analysed and disseminated for their future development, policy recommendations and recommendations on Living Lab methodology development.

Living Labs – definitions and methodologies

What is a Living Lab?

There is no single official or generally accepted definition for Living Labs applied consistently in literature or practice. However, all their different applications fall to the broader category of real-world testing grounds of innovative approaches (Rădulescu et al. 2022), innovations broadly understood as “the use of new ideas, products or methods where they have not been used before” (EUROSTAT Glossary 2023). Capturing their concurring characteristics, the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) defines Living Labs as “open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations and businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders. In this context, living labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators among citizens, research organisations, companies and government agencies/levels.” (ENoLL 2023).

Some references to ‘Living Laboratories’ as open and experimental learning and innovation environments were made in Europe already in 1990s (Rădulescu et al. 2022), but the term Living Lab was coined at Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in early 2000s to refer to *in vivo* settings of testing research hypotheses and technologies by experimenting and observing in living spaces. Soon after, the Living Labs flourished in Europe as more user-involving open innovation systems (Dutilleul et al. 2010). In 2006, the European Commission started to fund projects focusing on developing a common European innovation system based on Living Labs (European Commission 2009), under the EU presidency of Finland a Helsinki manifesto was launched that promoted Living Labs as a way to boost Europe’s economic competitiveness (Finland’s EU Presidency 2006), and the same year, the ENoLL was launched. As of today, there are over 480 Living Labs listed in Europe and beyond (ENoLL 2023).

Following the ENoLL definition, Malmberg et al. (2017) further detail **common characteristics** for Living Labs. First, Living Labs apply multi-method approaches to co-creation, with tailored methodologies for each

setting. Second, they emphasize the importance of involving end-users already at the beginning of process. According to Dutilleul et al. 2010, Living Labs constitute “new social configurations for organising innovation” and provide a platform for the key parties required in a joint problem-solving process. Third, Living Labs generally involve all actors of the Quadruple Helix Model (UNESCO and UNU-EGOV, 2016) including citizens, government, industry and academia, the Labs operating as intermediaries among the involved actors (Figure 2). Fourth, the Living Lab activities take place in real-life settings. Fifth, and linking to all the other aspects listed, Living Labs are about co-creation rather than top-down introduced experimentations. Importantly, the Labs’ co-creation process should span from co-design and co-production to co-implementation.

According to Ståhlbröst and Holst (2012), there are **five key principles** for Living Labs: 1) they should add value, 2) enable influence of end-users, 3) ensure sustainability of both the Lab process and of its impacts, 4) be based on openness including inclusion and transparency of the process, and 5) keep in mind realism regarding the Lab’s contexts, users, use-situations, innovations in focus and partners.

Temporally, Living Labs present iterative feedback processes aiming to create sustainable impact, with an open-ended timeline. Views differ on whether Living Labs should have a pre-set end-date. On the one hand the time limitation may restrict the innovation process, on the other the Living Labs may provide a valuable input just by supporting a co-creation focused period during e.g. project duration after which new arrangements can be made (Ståhlbröst and Holst 2012).

Figure 2. Quadruple helix of actors (UNESCO and UNU-EGOV, 2016).

By their **organisational model**, Living Labs have been classified by Schuurman (2015) to *macro* level with a territorial link, typically representing extensive public-private-people partnerships; they may operate at *meso* level, e.g. inside an organisation or at a project level in specific location; or at a *micro* level, focusing on a more limited number of uses and users and their specific actions. Marvin et al. (2018) provide another typology of Living Labs based on their initiators and leaders including *strategic* (led by governments or large private sector actors), *civic* (led e.g. by regional or local authorities or research institutes), or *grassroots* (led by civil society organisations or groups).

Living Labs can be **physical or virtual spaces**. Accordingly, their number of members or engaged stakeholders can vary, ranging from few to several thousands, especially in Living Labs established as virtual communities or platforms (Water Europe 2022).

Spatially, especially with the macro level Living Labs, the boundaries of the Labs do not always need to be geographical or managerial (e.g. a specific river basin or catchment, a region or nation, or an urban area).

According to Gamache et al. (2020), defining the boundaries of the Living Lab by the network of actors that compose it is likely more relevant, as it can also better equip and empower the stakeholders in question to implement the innovation in focus (see also sub-section “Living Labs as vehicles for sustainability transition”).

Although the information and communications technologies (ICT) sector was the first one in which the Living Lab concept arose, from a **topic** standpoint Living Labs today cover a broad variety of issues ranging from urban design to infrastructure, increasingly focusing on niche innovations for sustainability transition in a range of sectors (Gamache et al. 2020, Hossain et al. 2019). While they still typically have technology development at their core, the Labs are more and more embracing also social innovation (Dutilleul et al., 2019). The Living Lab approach is increasingly utilised for **policy planning** as a distinction from **product-orientated** original focus (Rădulescu et al. 2022), the GOVAQUA Living Labs building connections between the two.

Finally, coming back to the earlier notion of Living Labs falling to the broader category of real-world testing grounds of innovative approaches (Rădulescu et al. 2022), what differentiates them from e.g. Communities of practice (Wenger 1998, 2006), Demo Sites or Field Labs applied e.g. in various concurring European research projects (see e.g. RETOUCH NEXUS ID:101086522 and InnWater ID:101086512 funded from the same call with GOVAQUA) is that Living Labs tend to have a more systematic and institutionalised approach to innovation. How the practical application of the different approaches differs is another matter, and demands a reflective research effort.

Living Lab methodologies

As Malmberg et al. (2017) emphasize, there is no single Living Lab methodology. Generally, the approaches follow iterative and participatory process designs with a variety of available methods and tools which can be applied at different stages of the innovation process. ENoLL lists a variety of toolkits and toolboxes constructed and tips and tricks collected in previous Living Labs projects and programmes. Living Lab Handbooks have been produced by EU funded clusters and projects (e.g. Malmberg et al. 2017, Ståhlbröst and Holst 2012).

For the GOVAQUA Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations, three recent methodologies stand out: the three phases of innovation process proposed by Malmberg et al. (2017), the five phases of Living Labs proposed by Rădulescu et al. (2022), and the Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLs) methodology (Water Europe 2022) development under the Water4All partnership (Water4All 2023).

First, while primarily intended for product-orientated Living Labs, the **three phases of innovation process proposed by Malmberg et al. (2017)** provide a logical sequencing for the Labs’ work during the project’s duration, and in the case of GOVAQUA, help to link the Labs to the current and desired water governance situations and sustainability transition aims in the Labs’ settings. The phases include 1) Exploration: getting to know the ‘current state’ and describing possible and desired ‘future states’; 2) Experimentation: real-life testing of selected innovative instruments and approaches to reach the proposed ‘future states’; and 3) Evaluation: assessing the impact of the experiment with regards to the ‘current state’ in order to reach the ‘future state’ (after Malmberg et al. 2017).

Second, emphasizing the policy planning-orientated nature of the Labs fitting to the purposes of the GOVAQUA project, the **five phases of Living Labs proposed by Rădulescu et al. (2022)** building on Steen and Van Bueren (2017) add further steps to take into consideration: Initiation, Preparation, Co-Creative Design, Evaluation and Link with Decision-Making, and Feedback. According to Rădulescu et al. (2022), Initiation of a Lab can be sparked by complex or even wicked problems such as water governance

challenges, the initiator typically representing public or private research or civil society organization as in the case of GOVAQUA partners. The Preparation phase focuses on identification and engaging stakeholders with initial ‘allies’ and setting up the process design and management structure for the Lab. Co-creative design phase includes planning and design of the sessions, concurring ‘temperature checks’ to monitor progress and re-steer direction when needed, a flexible attitude and open and transparent communication. Evaluation and Link with Formal Decision-Making “acts as a linking pin with the decision-making process that can lead either to the formal blending in of the LL ‘product’ and therefore to its development and implementation, or to its failure to gain political support” (Rădulescu et al. 2022). The final Feedback step ends the Living Lab process and provides an opportunity for all the Living Lab stakeholders to reflect on the experiences and outcomes of the process regardless of the decisions on further development and implementation of the innovative instrument or approach in focus.

Third, the currently ongoing **Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLS) methodology development (Water Europe 2022) under the Water4All partnership (Water4All 2023)** provides additional aspects to consider.

The WOLLS methodology was originally proposed by Water Europe, the European Technology Platform for Water created by the European Commission in 2004, whose aim is to represent the whole value-chain of water and achieve a European Water-Smart Society. Water Europe defines WOLLS as “water-oriented, real-life demonstration and implementation instruments that bring together public and private institutions, government, civil society, and academia to jointly build structured grounds to develop, validate, and scale-up innovations that embrace new technologies, governance, business models, and advancing innovative policies to achieve a Water-Smart Society” (Water Europe 2022).

Figure 3. Visualization of the Harmonization Cube (Water Europe 2022).

Water Europe compiled the first Atlas of EU Water-Oriented Living Labs in 2018-2019 following and applying the rationale of the Water Europe Water Vision. The current WOLLs methodology follows the same logic of mapping and assessing existing WOLLs based on the Harmonization Cube (Figure 3) method, which “after an extensive bibliographic review” was considered by Water Europe to be the best available assessment tool, and has also been adopted as a best practice by ENOLL. The aim is to further tailor the Harmonization Cube method to the water sector, to allow for the coordinated assessment, analysis, synergic development, harmonization, and networking of local, municipal and regional WOLL initiatives.

The WOLLs methodology uses as a starting point the six aspects (or foundational elements) representing the essential characterization of a Living Lab according to Mulder et al. (2008): User involvement; Service creation; Infrastructure; Governance; Innovation outcomes; Methods & tools. These six foundational elements of any Living Lab are then assessed through a Harmonization Cube, which provides detailed evaluation criteria for each of them (the six faces of the cube representing the six elements; Figure 3).

Each face of the cube includes a 3x3 evaluation matrix: on the horizontal axis organizational, contextual and technological perspectives; and on the vertical axis the three development phases of a LL life cycle: setup, sustainability, and scalability (Figure 4). Each foundational element of a Living Lab can hence be assessed, using 3x3= 9 criteria, to establish its development phase and opportunities to further increase their impact on the implementation of (water) innovations, by improving its organizational set-up, the way it interacts with its environment (contextual) and the way it leverages technologies to optimize support for the research, development, and innovation processes.

Figure 4. The 9 evaluation perspectives of the cube (Water Europe 2022).

While the WOLLs methodology is the most comprehensive Living Lab methodology focusing on water management and governance aspects, as noted, it is still predominantly focused on assessing the advanced stages of the Living Labs: monitoring the evolution of their organization and their maturity levels, the actual results of the Living Lab against expectations, and the satisfaction levels of participating actors. Hence, in its current form it is not directly suited for establishing new WOLLs.

GOVAQUA’s Living Labs process design is intended for this purpose - for designing and setting up new Labs of water governance innovations, building on the process phases by Malmberg et al. (2017) and Rădulescu

et al. (2022). To build bridges with the different complementary methodologies, the GOVAQUA project will collaborate with the Water4All Pillar D during the project duration in developing the Harmonization Cube-based WOLLS methodology to further include design, policy planning and sustainability transition aspects, with first joint workshops outlined for 2024. Furthermore, possibilities to assess the GOVAQUA Living Labs as a part of the forthcoming WOLLS Atlas assessments will be explored.

The phases and detailed content of the GOVAQUA Living Lab process bringing together selected aspects from the three main Living Lab methodologies by Malmberg et al. (2017), Rădulescu et al. (2022) and Water Europe (2022) as detailed above will be presented below in section “GOVAQUA Living Lab process design”.

Living Labs as vehicles for sustainability transitions

While the primary function of the GOVAQUA Living Labs is to act as real-world testing grounds for water governance innovations with the leadership of work package (WP) 6 partners, in the GOVAQUA project they are also studied as vehicles for sustainability transitions. In this endeavour, with the primary leadership of GOVAQUA WP1 partners, following aspects are initially incorporated to the GOVAQUA Living Lab process design as described below, but addressing them demands a reflective research effort throughout the Living Lab process.

In sustainability transitions literature, experimentation has been studied widely over the past decade and Living Labs are recognised as spaces for experimentation and learning towards transition. Within this context, experimentation refers to “an inclusive, practice-based and challenge-led initiative, which is designed to promote system innovation” (Sengers et al, 2019, p. 153). In this literature, experimentation is perceived as an alternative mode of governance to address climate change and other wicked societal challenges (Bulkeley et al. 2016; Evans et al. 2016). Such experiments take five main forms: niche, bounded socio-technical, transition, grassroots and sustainability experiments. What niche, socio-technical, transition, grassroots experiments have in common is that they promote radical – as opposed to incremental – innovation and involve the development and testing of technical or social innovations outside existing (governance) regimes. Sustainability experiments differ in the sense that they can be planned by governments as well (i.e. regime actors) (Sengers et al, 2019). Within this context, a regime is generally understood as a combination of material and technical elements, actor networks and formal, normative and cognitive rules that guide the activities of actors (Geels, 2004). Regime actors (including governments) are often referred to as “incumbent actors”. From a transition management perspective, collaboration between diverse actors who operate outside the incumbent regime, i.e. frontrunners who seek innovation and do not represent existing institutions or an organization with an interest, is a critical factor (Loorbach, 2010). At the same time, the concept of Urban Living Labs has gained prominence in recent years. These studies often bridge between urban planning and transition studies acknowledging the importance of collaboration between governments, private sectors, citizens and academics (Rizzo et al, [2021](#)).

As noted, Living Labs are widely perceived as catalysts for innovations. Yet, they differ greatly in terms of goals, activities, participants and context (Gamache et al. 2020). With regard to **goals**, like the literature on sustainability transitions, GOVAQUA adopts a normative orientation on experimentation with sustainable and equitable water use being the desired, shared goal for all GOVAQUA Living Labs. An element to consider here is the extent to which Living Labs empower participants and allow for autonomous thinking, knowledge development and gaining experience (Gamache et al. 2020). With regards to the need to transform, in contrast to many studies focusing on experimentation in transition studies, GOVAQUA is not

necessarily about radical innovation and engaging frontrunners only. Rather the focus of GOVAQUA is on innovation (be it incremental or radical) within the scope and realm of existing governance structures.

With regard to **activities**, transition management emphasizes that sufficient time and flexibility is needed for 1) problem (re)structuring (integration of diverse perspectives); 2) envisioning and formation of a challenging vision; and 3) development of a transition agenda (Scholz et al. 2020). True innovation in GOVAQUA Living Labs is likely to be achieved only when sufficient attention is paid to these elements in the Exploration phase as further detailed in the section below.

With regard to **participants**, recent studies have started moving away from the initial dichotomy between radical niche actors (frontrunners) versus incumbent regime actors that aim for incremental change or impose change (Köhler et al. 2019). Research that combines social learning and transition perspectives shows that collaboration with government actors – who have the right mindset and an adequate understanding and influence on formal decision-making processes – is critical for innovation processes to have an impact (Scholz et al. 2020). As water governance is primarily led and under the mandate of governments, the engagement of the public and government actors is central in all the GOVAQUA Living Labs. Furthermore, the relative importance of decentralised and informal processes also depends on whether the transition is in an early or later stage (Rijke et al, 2013). For innovations that emerge in informal networks to have an impact, collaboration with formal institutions is of critical importance (Dobre et al, 2018).

Finally, transition studies do yield key lessons on the relationship between an innovation (process) and its **context**. In other words, understanding an innovation's structural impact on the water governance regime. First, the compatibility between an innovation and its environment can be 'fit and conform' (in tune with the regime) or 'stretch and transform' (demanding structural changes in the existing regime) (Smith and Raven 2012). Research into how the relationship between an innovation process and its institutional context might change over time shows that at least three different situations can occur. An innovation process can be characterized as: 1) "pave the way for change" (considerable influence on the institutional context); 2) "easy ride" (changes to the institutional context are supportive of pursued change); or 3) "roadblock" (institutional context becomes less supportive of pursued change) (Beers & Van Mierlo, 2017). Changes in the institutional context may occur due to societal learning process or an event opening a window of opportunity (Vinke-de Kruijf et al, 2020). These aspects are especially important to consider during the Evaluation and feedback phase of the Living Labs as described below. They also provide an interesting reflective research task throughout the Living Lab process.

GOVAQUA Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations

The GOVAQUA Living Lab process design as detailed in the next section is built on the experiences and guidance on good practices of Living Lab applications in the European context and the key notions from the sustainability transition literature as described above.

The working definition for the GOVAQUA Living Labs at this stage is "An innovation ecosystem where societal stakeholders and researchers collaboratively explore, experiment with and evaluate one or more water governance innovations".

The design will allow for certain flexibility during the different stages of the innovation process, taking into consideration differences between the GOVAQUA Labs regarding their levels of current maturity, policy planning vs. product orientation and forms of stakeholder engagement. All the Living Labs share certain key

characteristic, however. Their ‘future states’ should be connected to the targets of the European Green Deal, Water Framework Directive and UN Sustainable Development Goals, and despite the project-type intervention, they will be linked to the catchment, local, basin or national water governance processes and actors in the given setting.

Furthermore, the common design is intended for lesson learning between the Living Labs and capturing key insights on thematic good practices and innovations in focus for European-wide policy development. Finally, as noted, the common design will enable an analysis of the value of Living Labs as potential vehicles of transition to sustainable and equitable water use in Europe, and feed to the broader guideline development of Living Labs under Water4All.

GOVAQUA Living Lab process design

The four phases of the GOVAQUA Living Lab process design built on the sequencing of Malmberg et al. (2017) and Rădulescu et al. (2022) are described in Figure 5 and detailed in the sub-sections below. While they are now presented in a chronological order, typically to the innovation process the different phases might also be overlapping, repeating and occurring in partially changing order (Malmberg et al. 2017). Nevertheless, due to the time-limitations of the GOVAQUA intervention, the Living Labs should seek to plan their work along the proposed timeline and joint steps.

Figure 5. The phases and key joint steps of the GOVAQUA Living Lab process design. The boxes detail the content of the tasks be carried out by the Labs in each phase with inputs from other work packages, whereas the timeline indicates joint meetings, workshops, milestones (M) and deliverables (D).

Furthermore, for each phase, **Core** and thus compulsory **tasks** and **methods and tools** are listed, with additional **Recommended reading** of reference documents, toolkits and guidance. Each section also details

the foreseen linkages to other GOVAQUA project processes, events and outputs all Labs to consider. Their further details will be confirmed once the project proceeds.

In the Living Lab processes, the prescribed methods and tools should not rule over the overall aim – identifying, further developing, and validating the value of innovative water governance instruments and approaches with key stakeholders. The details of process can be adjusted to the Lab’s context in consultation with the WP6 leaders. However, during each of the phases of the Labs lessons should be recorded on the suitability of the process design and the Lab approach itself, whether they serve their purpose in practice and, to the extent possible, in facilitating transition to sustainable and equitable water use in Europe.

Initiation and preparation phase

How to get started?

Core

While the GOVAQUA Living Labs all have their roots in pre-existing multi-stakeholder initiatives, it is strongly encouraged to have a strategic and practical plan for their execution during the project timeline.

For the **strategic planning of the Living Labs**, [strategic canvas from the GoNano project](#) or a similar template is recommended. For the **practical planning of the Living Labs**, the [practical canvas of the GoNano project](#) or similar template can be used. When detailing the Living Lab timeline, see the sections below and the GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal), which will be updated as the project proceeds.

For identifying stakeholders and planning stakeholder engagement as a part of the canvases, see the list of issues to consider and possible tools to utilise in the section below. It is important to do pre-scanning and validation of the pre-selected Living Labs topics with selected key ‘allies’ (Rădulescu et al. 2022). It is also important to identify linkages and necessary alignment with other potentially ongoing processes to avoid stakeholder fatigue and to ensure their buy-in.

While the GOVAQUA Living Labs have been resourced by the project funding, sustainability of the Labs after the GOVAQUA intervention is good to also give due consideration. Additional funding options might be available e.g., via Water4All partnership programme by the European Commission or from national or regional innovation funding or development programmes.

Timing, practicalities and linkages

While the GOVAQUA Living Labs are intended to commence in August 2023 (Month (M)7), their initiation and preparation work can start before the actual beginning date. **A consortium internal Initiation and preparation phase online meeting** will be organised in early September 2023 (M8). Each of the Living Labs are also strongly encouraged to arrange an **internal online workshop** to go through the different initiation and preparation aspects by the end of September (see also the next section).

A key component linking the GOVAQUA Living Labs to other GOVAQUA Work Packages will be an **Excel-based open survey distributed to the Living Lab leaders** in June-early September 2023 (M5-7), collecting insights from the Living Labs on key interlinkages to consider.

For further details, see the GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal).

Recommended reading

- Rădulescu, M.A., Leendertse, W., Arts, J. (2022). Living Labs: A Creative and Collaborative Planning Approach. In: Franklin, A. (eds) Co-Creativity and Engaged Scholarship. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-84248-2_15
- ENOLL (2023) *Toolkits*. Available at: <https://enoll.org/toolkits/>
- Van Mierlo, B. C., Regeer, B., van Amstel, M., Arkesteijn, M. C. M., Beekman, V., Bunders, J. F. G., ... & Leeuwis, C. (2010). *Reflexive monitoring in action. A guide for monitoring system innovation projects*. Communication and Innovation Studies, WUR; Athena Institute, VU. <https://edepot.wur.nl/149471>

Who to involve and how?

Core

Several **stakeholder analysis methods** are available for identifying, differentiating, categorising, and investigating the relationships between stakeholders of water resources management and governance question in focus in the GOVAQUA Living Labs (Reed et al. 2009).

For **stakeholder identification, focus group discussions, semi-structured interviews and snowball sampling** are recommended methods (for details, see Reed et al. 2009).

For **stakeholder classification**, a good first step is a **Rainbow diagram** (Chevalier and Buckles 2008) (see illustration e.g., in [Hoppenbrouwers et al. 2014](#)) placing the stakeholders on a spectrum reflecting the degree they are affecting or being affected by the water governance challenge in question, or by the envisioned action. In addition to typical classification to water users, regulators and water service providers, expert community, non-governmental organisations and different, also vulnerable social groups need to be taken into consideration as well. After this step, it is useful to further classify the stakeholders to key categories, e.g., 1) those to actively engage, 2) those to keep informed, 3) those to monitor, and 4) those to keep satisfied (see also GOVAQUA D7.1 DEC Plan Target groups). Again, careful attention should be given to explore ways to engage the under-represented, disadvantaged, or marginalised groups as identified on the Rainbow diagram.

Further **investigation of relationships between stakeholders** is useful for understanding and positioning the interaction processes and linkages between different stakeholders (i.e., which parties are possible enablers or gatekeepers of the innovation), and accordingly for planning the timing and prioritisation for their engagement.

A crucial aspect to consider is that the Living Labs focusing on water governance are not politically neutral, and may become “arenas of unequal expectations for various kinds of stakeholders, power games due to the influence and power of different actors, therefore leading to conflicts” (Rădulescu et al. 2022). When designed well, however, the Living Labs may help to overcome previous problems and provide a neutral arena for the stakeholders to come together. Possibility to link the Labs to pre-existing and ongoing initiatives should be carefully explored to ensure efficient use of resources and to avoid stakeholder fatigue.

As emphasised, for the water governance issues in focus of GOVAQUA, the role and processes of public sector agencies are especially important to consider. The Living Labs may form a parallel process to official planning and decision making, but in order to manage expectations, it should be made clear that the innovations the Living Labs produce do not necessarily end up taken up in the official processes (Rădulescu et al. 2022).

When the stakeholders have been classified, for the **stakeholder engagement** the stakeholders are useful to position on **stakeholder – Living Lab phase – matrix (e.g., in a table format)** to detail who to involve at the different phases of the Living Lab process. It is worthwhile to keep in mind that while inclusivity is a priority, too large a group of participants may hinder the co-creation process. Hence representation of stakeholders within the Living Lab participants needs to be considered carefully. It is advisable to start the engagement with the core groups and then gradually proceed to inviting and informing others.

The actual ways and means to organise the co-creation process with the Living Lab participants depend on the given Living Lab context and setting. **ENoLL** lists a variety of **toolkits and toolboxes** with facilitation methods suited for different phases of the Living Labs.

A crucial aspect to consider throughout the Living Lab process from setting its original aims to process design, the actual co-creation process and final outputs, is **incorporation of gender aspects**. Gender sensitivity in water governance research and practice means addressing the desires, needs and interests of all genders with regards to water access, use and decision-making. Furthermore, gender equality in participation has been shown to provide critical complementary perspectives.

To ensure adequate incorporation of gender aspects, each of the GOVAQUA Living Lab project teams should apply the **GenderWave tool** (Valve 2020) (developed in the H2020 Baltic Gender project) that will help to explicate how the gender aspects can be addressed throughout the given Living Lab process. While the GenderWater tool is originally intended for marine research and innovation projects, the questions it asks are directly applicable to freshwater governance as well (see Valve 2020 p.9 onwards). It is important to record down the Living Lab specific answers to the questions for the Living Lab reporting purposes (see the section “Living Labs coordination and synthesis of lessons learned”). As general guidelines, the Living Labs should maximize the creation and use of **gender-disaggregated data**, as promoted by SDG5 on gender equality. Furthermore, as the Living Lab experiments will be mobilised in different contexts, they also offer opportunities for learning about gender-related implementation of innovative governance approaches relevant for the project considerations and recommendations of good practices.

Timing, practicalities and linkages

As indicated in the previous section, a **consortium internal Initiation and preparation phase online meeting for the GOVAQUA Living Lab leaders** will be organised in early September 2023 (M8), and each of the Living Labs are strongly encouraged to arrange an **internal online workshop** to go through the different initiation and preparation aspects by the end of September.

When getting in touch with the stakeholders with whom direct engagement is planned, an appropriate **introduction to the GOVAQUA project including funding statements** should be given. Make sure to use the **GOVAQUA templates, logos and visualisations provided by WP7**. The work on the strategic canvas should also help in crystallizing in e.g. a one pager to be used with the invitations: 1) what the Living Lab is about, 2) what it aims for, 3) why the given stakeholders are invited, 4) when and how they are asked to commit, and 5) how they will benefit from the process.

Building on the stakeholder analysis, also consider the overall dissemination and communication strategy for your Living Lab: which channels and formats are you going to use? For further details, see the D7.1 GOVAQUA DEC Plan. The DEC aspects will also be covered in the consortium internal meeting.

For further details, see the GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal).

Recommended reading

- Reed, M.S, Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Prell, C., Quinn, C.H., Stringer, L.C. (2009) Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural

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- ENOLL (2023) *Toolkits*. Available at: <https://enoll.org/toolkits/>

Exploration phase

Core

The actual co-creation process of the Living Labs starts with an Exploration phase focusing on three tasks **1) understanding and benchmarking the current water governance setting with the selected stakeholders, 2) defining desired future states, and 3) co-designing the innovative instrument/approach/model to be tested** to help in reaching the desired future state.

A consortium internal Exploration phase online meeting will be organised for the Living Lab leaders, after which each Living Lab is to organise **a kick-off workshop with stakeholders** (see subsection on Timing, practicalities and linkages below for further details). The kick-off workshop is important for clarifying the co-creation process objectives and agreeing on joint ways of working (Rădulescu et al. 2022). **A series of stakeholder workshop sessions** linked to the **tasks 1-3 listed above** are advisable. Furthermore, for each of the tasks, analyses and tools will be provided by the project and supporting methods are proposed as described below.

For understanding and benchmarking the current setting with stakeholders, there is a possibility to utilise a background **policy and regulatory analysis** conducted by GOVAQUA WP2 at EU and national level, if relevant and needed for the specific Living Lab process. The analysis focus can be further defined based on the Living Lab needs in consultation with the WP2 partners, and its findings can be further validated by the stakeholder participants.

For defining the desired future states, GOVAQUA WP1 will develop a **GOVAQUA self-assessment tool** to be applied by the Living Lab participants, providing a structured status check of the challenges at hand and then focusing on setting ambitions for a transition to a more advanced state. The assessment findings can then be utilised in 1) validating the initially selected instrument/approach/model to be tested, and 2) further co-designing them towards achieving the set ambitions. For this purpose, also the **good practices** related to **innovative legal and regulatory approaches** from WP2, **participatory and collaborative approaches** from WP3, **economic and financial instruments** from WP4, and **digital solutions for information** sharing from WP5 can be utilised.

In all the stakeholder workshops, additional **brainstorming, ideation and co-creation techniques** listed by ENOLL can be utilised. Following Malmberg et al. (2017), besides stakeholder workshops, **observation and participation in related governance processes and interventions** and **in-depth interviews with key stakeholders** by the Living Lab responsible partners can further support the exploration activities. To ensure broad stakeholder buy-in for the Living Lab process, however, joint workshops are needed to reach a shared understanding of the current situation, desired future state and selecting the governance instruments/approaches/models to be further co-produced and tested in the following phases.

Timing, practicalities and linkages

The Exploration phase is proposed to be started in October 2023 (M9) with the **consortium internal Exploration phase online meeting** with the Living Lab leaders and the additional WP1, WP2 and WP3

expert partners. After that, the **Living Lab kick-off** should be arranged latest in November-December 2023 (M10-11). However, the preliminary national policy and regulatory analyses from WP2 will be available only by the end of November, the exact timing to be confirmed with the Living Lab partners, who will themselves play a key role in supporting the analyses.

A **consortium internal GOVAQUA self-assessment tool workshop 1** led by WP1 will be organised with Living Lab teams and experts from other WPs in January-February 2024 (M13), introducing the GOVAQUA self-assessment tool. The second stakeholder workshop session can then be organised in February-May 2024 (M13-16), applying the self-assessment tool. **Consortium internal GOVAQUA self-assessment tool workshop 2** to gather lessons learned from the first application of the assessment tool in the Living Labs and needs for refinement will be organised in June 2024 (M17). The Assessment tool will be applied again in the Living Labs in the Evaluation and feedback phase. The **good practices from the thematic WPs** are available by September 2024 (M20), after which a third stakeholder workshop focusing on co-designing the instrument/approach/model in focus can be organised.

For a proposal of a more detailed timeline and workshop series, see the GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal).

The data collection approach for the QCA undertaken in WP1 Task 1.3 will also be tested in the Exploration phase by the WP1 experts who will conduct interviews with selected actors involved in the Living Labs and review secondary sources to triangulate and validate the findings. The aim of the QCA is to determine to what extent and under which conditions specific water governance innovations contribute to a transition towards more sustainable and equitable water governance.

WP3 team is available to support the Living Labs with points of attention for social equity and justice in stakeholder analysis and selection, and methodological aspects regarding cross-sectoral collaboration and stakeholder participation. In addition, exploratory interviews are envisioned to be carried out by the WP3 experts to capture the stakeholders' perception of the current participatory status, including the problems and improvement areas in the broader governance setting of the Living Labs.

Recommended reading

- Malmberg, K., Vaittinen, I., Evans, P., Schuurman, D., Ståhlbröst, A. & Vervoort, K. (2017). *Living Lab Methodology Handbook*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1146321>
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Experimentation phase

Core

The Experimentation phase focuses on the knowledge **co-production**, i.e., **further development and testing of the selected governance innovation in focus**. The aim is to gather “user reactions and attitudes to the proposed solutions, and to also capture behaviour, which is made possible by having the testing take place in “as-real-life-as-possible” contexts” (Malmberg et al. 2017).

The actual content of the Experimentation phase will be defined by the Exploration phase findings. As each of the GOVAQUA Living Labs will likely focus on different types of innovative instruments, approaches and models, various methods with varying intensities of stakeholder involvement can be applied in the Experimentation. Again, the **ENoLL listed toolkits** are recommended to be utilised. Besides co-production

techniques in **stakeholder workshops**, other research-driven methods such as **stakeholder surveys** and **interviews** can be applied.

Timing, practicalities and linkages

A **consortium internal Experimentation phase online meeting** will be organised for the Living Lab leaders in autumn 2024, tentatively at the beginning in October 2024 (M21). The Experimentation phase is envisioned to take place between October 2024 (M21) and May 2025 (M28).

A key interaction with the other GOVAQUA work packages relates to **validation of the initial list of good practices** delivered at the end of the Exploration phase to the Living Labs (see the section above), the final versions of the good practices being due from the thematic work packages in July 2025 (M30).

For a proposal of a more detailed timeline and workshop series, see the GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal).

Recommended reading

- Malmberg, K., Vaittinen, I., Evans, P., Schuurman, D., Ståhlbröst, A. & Vervoort, K. (2017). *Living Lab Methodology Handbook*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1146321>
- Rădulescu, M.A., Leendertse, W., Arts, J. (2022). Living Labs: A Creative and Collaborative Planning Approach. In: Franklin, A. (eds) *Co-Creativity and Engaged Scholarship*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-84248-2_15
- ENoLL (2023) *Toolkits*. Available at: <https://enoll.org/toolkits/>

Evaluation and feedback phase

Core

After the co-production and selected multi-method testing of the water governance innovation in focus in the Experimentation phase, **the findings should be brought together and evaluated with the stakeholders in a stakeholder workshop**. A key component in the evaluation will be the **second application of the assessment tool**. As Malmberg et al. (2017 p. 16) put it, “the Evaluation stage enables to generate a ‘post-measurement’ of the intervention and compare it to the ‘pre-measurement’ benchmark, illustrating potential impact and added-value created by the innovation.”

The Evaluation and feedback phase should give an indication whether the stakeholders should proceed to further co-implementation with the innovation, with associated policy recommendations and guidance for water and water-using sectors and citizens, when applicable. This phase should also include consideration of the sustainability and impact of the project intervention – what will happen next? It is an important time for re-checking linkages to other platforms and processes. Here, feedback from especially public sector agencies responsible for water related planning and management is important to gather.

Lessons learned from the Living Labs will also be gathered for the broader project recommendation purposes in WP1 (Task 1.4 synthesis and Task 1.5 transition pathways), and a **final workshop for all the GOVAQUA Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations** will provide an opportunity to bring all the Living Lab stakeholders together for broader lesson learning. Possibilities to include the GOVAQUA Living Labs in the WOLLs Atlas assessment will also be explored with Water Europe.

Timing, practicalities and linkages

A **consortium internal Evaluation phase online meeting** will be organised for the Living Lab leaders in June-August 2025 (M29-31). The Evaluation phase in the Living Labs may span from September 2025 to May

2026, during which time a **workshop for the second application of the assessment tool** should be organised, with the **Final workshop of the Living Labs** due in May 2026 (M40) and the **Living Lab reports and other pre-seen outputs** in July 2026 (M42).

WP6 leaders (CETAQUA and Syke) will compile a **Report recording recommendations of Living Labs a) on specific innovations and b) as vehicles of sustainability transition** in water governance by September 2026 (M44). The Living Lab findings will also contribute towards publications under WP1.

For a proposal of a more detailed timeline and workshop series, see the GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal).

Recommended reading

- Malmberg, K., Vaittinen, I., Evans, P., Schuurman, D., Ståhlbröst, A. & Vervoort, K. (2017). *Living Lab Methodology Handbook*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1146321>
- Rădulescu, M.A., Leendertse, W., Arts, J. (2022). Living Labs: A Creative and Collaborative Planning Approach. In: Franklin, A. (eds) *Co-Creativity and Engaged Scholarship*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-84248-2_15
- ENoLL (2023) *Toolkits*. Available at: <https://enoll.org/toolkits/>
- Water Europe (2022). Water-Oriented Living Labs: Notebook Series #1. Definitions, practices and assessment methods. Available at: https://watereurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/WoLL-Notebook-Series2_2pages.pdf

Living Labs coordination and synthesis of lessons learned

Coordination of the whole Living Lab process is required to ensure harmonisation of methodologies, as well as comparable and complementary results, avoiding unnecessary duplicated analyses. This coordination will be ensured by putting into practice the following actions:

- Set up of a joint digital platform (primarily GOVAQUA Teams) for sharing documents, results and lessons learned, and facilitate the exchange of information among Living Labs by using similar folders organisation. Additionally, each Living Lab may set up its own platform for coordination and sharing of documents with its stakeholders.
- Organisation of **five online meetings, coinciding with the beginning of each main phase of the Living Lab process design: Initiation and preparation, Exploration, Experimentation, Evaluation and feedback, and the Final workshop**. These workshops need to be attended by all Living Lab leaders and should establish the basis for the subsequent development of each Living Lab phase.
- Organisation of periodic coordination meetings between Living Lab leaders and thematic WP leaders. A quarterly frequency has been preliminary established, although it will be adapted to emerging needs. These meetings will serve to update the status of Living Labs and WPs, and ensure coordination among all responsible partners.

Organisation of additional coordination meetings and, if necessary, **preparation of guidelines summarising specific methodologies**, are also foreseen. Coordination meetings will also serve as platforms for knowledge sharing between partners and to check implementation progress in the different Living Labs.

As noted under the Evaluation and feedback phase, each Living Lab will produce a **report synthesising the lessons learned** during WP6 implementation, a template for which will be provided in early Autumn 2023. These reports will include recorded findings during the different process design phases (Initiation and

preparation, Exploration, Experimentation, and Evaluation and feedback), the inputs from WPs 2-5 the Living Labs have used, and how they have adapted them to the specific local circumstances, as well as initial recommendations on how those lessons could be applied in other European contexts.

Finally, a document detailing **GOVAQUA recommendations on Living Labs of Water Governance Innovations** will be prepared based on the collated Living Lab findings towards the end of the project. Additional guidance on good practice of water governance Living Labs may be developed in collaboration with Water Europe under the Water4All Partnership Pillar D along the project timeframe.

For a proposal of a more detailed timeline and coordination tasks, see GOVAQUA Living Labs GANTT-chart (consortium internal).

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